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Enhancing Cross-Border Risk Assessment for Critical Infrastructure: Challenges, Tools and Recommendations

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Extended Abstract

The Directive on Resilience of Critical Entities (Directive (EU) 2022/2557) outlines that each Member State (MS) should carry out, within a harmonised framework, an assessment of the relevant natural and man-made risks, as well as those of a cross-sectoral or cross-border nature, that could affect the provision of essential services. The risk assessment by MSs should integrate a wide range of hazards, from accidents, natural disasters and public health emergencies to hybrid threats or other antagonistic threats, including terrorist offences, criminal infiltration and sabotage (Art. 5).

Moreover, the actions of MSs to identify and help ensure the resilience of critical entities should follow a risk-based approach that focuses on the entities most relevant for the performance of vital societal functions or economic activities. When conducting their risk assessments, MSs should consider the extent to which sectors depend on one another, including sectors in other MSs and third countries.

The outcome of the MS risk assessments should be used for the purposes of identifying critical entities (Art. 6) and assisting those entities in meeting their resilience requirements (Art. 13).

To facilitate the development of a cohesive framework across the EU, this analysis explores the complexities and challenges of conducting cross-border risk assessments for critical infrastructure (CI) and associated critical entities, from a conceptual perspective.

The study begins by examining the current state of National Risk Assessments (NRAs), highlighting discrepancies, heterogeneity of competences as well as the lack of a harmonised framework and coherent terminology across MSs. NRAs frequently overlook future changes and neglect cross-border risks, focusing on individual hazards and failing to account for compound events and systemic impacts.

This JRC work underscores the importance of adopting a holistic approach to assess risks to CI that may have low likelihood but potentially high impact, as well as an all-hazards perspective that includes spill-over effects and interconnected risks. Such approach is essential for fully grasping the systemic vulnerabilities of critical infrastructure, which may be exacerbated by dependencies on sectors in other MSs and third countries.

The study also explores the drivers of cross-border risk assessment, emphasising the need to address fast and slow onset phenomena and the dynamic linkages to climate change, environmental degradation, and urbanisation, which can rapidly transform the risk landscape. Additionally, the analysis highlights the impact causes, orders and categories of cross-border dependencies for CI, providing examples of impacts resulting from neighbouring countries and affecting multiple nations simultaneously.

Furthermore, the study introduces methods and tools for CI risk assessment, considering data inventory, spatial mapping, measuring metrics, and analytical products. It highlights the challenges of cross-border risk assessment, such as fragmentation, communication barriers, comparability, ownership, prioritization, and offers recommendations to address them.

In conclusion, the proposed approach underscores the importance of integrating impact and likelihood in MS risk assessments, understanding the type and magnitude of events, and recognising the potential hindrances to emergency response capabilities due to a CI disruption. It advocates for service-oriented approaches, harmonised information sharing, effective governance frameworks, and multi-stakeholder engagement as essential components of a robust cross-border risk assessment strategy to address the intricate interplay between risks and the knowledge associated to CI. These elements are vital not only for the management and reduction of risks but also for ensuring the resilience of critical entities across the EU.

References

Directive (EU) 2022/2557 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on the resilience of critical entities <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2022/2557/oj>

Decision (EU) 2019/420 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 March 2019 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019D0420>

List of abbreviations

CI	Critical Infrastructure
JRC	Joint Research Centre
MS	Member State
NRA	National Risk Assessment